

Dynamic State Estimation for Multi-Machine Power System Using Least Mean Square Algorithm

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Abstract—This paper presents a dynamic state estimation method based on the least mean square algorithm to increase adaptability to measurement data and reduce runtime. The proposed method can be used to estimate the rotor angle and speed of synchronous generators in real time from the terminal voltage and phase data measured using the phase measurement unit. The proposed method is compared with the extended Kalman filter-based method in a WSCC 9-bus system for three cases. The simulation results show that the RMSE of the estimation result in the proposed method decreased by at least 30% compared to the existing method, and the runtime also decreased from 0.6536 ms to 0.2439 ms. Therefore, the proposed method can be applied to power systems that are larger and contain many components. To the best of our knowledge, the proposed method is the first attempt to apply the LMS algorithm to power system dynamic state estimation.

Index Terms—Dynamic state estimation (DSE), least-mean-square (LMS), multi-machine, phasor measurement units (PMUs), synchronous generators

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENTLY, with the expansion of renewable energy, the penetration rate of distributed generators (DGs) in power systems has been rapidly increasing [1]. Since DGs can be installed near consumers, costs associated with transmission and distribution, infrastructure construction, and operation, as well as social costs can be reduced when introducing new facilities [2]. However, DGs can degrade power system stability because of its low short-circuit ratio and high variability [3]. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce a method to efficiently integrate the operation of DGs. Accordingly, it is necessary to develop a system that can perform real-time monitoring of the entire power system [4].

Existing supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA)-based approaches are limited in capturing fast dynamics within the system because of their slow sampling rate (2 to 4 s) [5]. However, more accurate and faster dynamic state estimation (DSE) can be achieved using a phase measurement unit (PMU), and related research is underway.

The Kalman filter is a commonly used method for implementing power system DSE. Z. Huang *et al.* [6] proposed an extended Kalman filter (EKF)-based method with a second-order generator model. The tests were performed on a WSCC 9-bus system, and the results demonstrated the feasibility of

the EKF-based DSE method. However, the EKF is a first-order Taylor series approximation to nonlinear functions, which is suitable for use in “mild” nonlinear environments, and it can only be applied in the presence of Jacobian matrices [7]. To solve these limitations, different methods such as the iterated EKF (IEKF) and unscented Kalman filter (UKF) have been developed. J. Zhao *et al.* [8] proposed an IEKF-based method for robustness and tested it on an IEEE-39 bus system. Their method iteratively linearizes nonlinear equations to reduce nonlinear error. G. Valverde *et al.* [9] proposed a UKF-based method and tested it on three test systems. More specifically, the method uses an approximation strategy through sampling based on the premise that it is easier to approximate a probability distribution than to linearize a nonlinear function. Y. Li *et al.* [10] proposed a robust cubature Kalman filter (RCKF)-based method and tested it on the WSCC 9-bus and IEEE-39 bus systems. Specifically, the method uses robust M-estimation to detect outliers in measurements and eliminates the detected outliers by revising the measurement noise variance matrix. In addition, several Kalman filter-based DSE methods have been proposed in [11]–[15]. Indeed, these methods can reduce nonlinear errors and increase robustness against outliers; however, they significantly increase the complexity of the algorithm. They are unsuitable for large systems because of their high computational power requirements [16], [17].

Previous studies have also explored AI-based data-driven approaches. Yu Yanjie *et al.* [18] proposed a DSE method featuring a CNN-LSTM predictor to enhance the estimation accuracy. Test results on the IEEE 33-bus system show improved accuracy. Haiing Li *et al.* [19] proposed a DSE method featuring a generative adversarial network (GAN) model that reconstructs measurement data to enhance the estimation robustness. The robustness of the expected performance has been demonstrated by testing on an IEEE 30-bus system. Guanyu Tian *et al.* [20] proposed a hybrid learning DSE that combines real-time data and physical models. The tests were conducted on an NPCC 140-bus system and convergence speed was significantly improved in large systems. Sassan Goleijani *et al.* [21] proposed a DSE method featuring ANN-based pseudo-measurement generation. The test was conducted on the IEEE 118-bus system, and the results confirm that bad data detection and identification performance was improved.

However, these studies are primarily focused on DSE performance for measurement outliers. Thus, a slow runtime performance may adversely affect control performance or may not be able to capture certain events that occur in the system, primarily because momentary cessation and recovery of a DG can occur within 10-20 ms [22]. Therefore, an extremely

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fast runtime performance is required to ensure stable system operation and analysis in multi-machine systems. Additionally, the burden of introducing monitoring systems (sensors, network infrastructure, database servers, etc.) makes it even more difficult to obtain data from generators [23]. Under such circumstances, it may be difficult to practically apply methods that require offline learning in advance. In short, runtime and computational burden must be reduced to maintain the stability of multi-machine systems.

In this paper, a DSE method based on the least mean square (LMS) algorithm is proposed. The rotor angle and speed are estimated from the PMU data using the 2nd order generator model and LMS algorithm. LMS weight updates are mathematically derived more compactly than EKF updates, resulting in shorter runtimes. The performance of the proposed method is verified by comparing with the performance of EKF in the WSCC 9-bus system. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the power system models applied to DSE. Section III presents the LMS-based DSE method. Moreover, the concept of the method and the simplicity of updating the formula are presented. Section IV presents the results of the LMS-based DSE method, and the results are analyzed by comparing with those of the EKF-based method. Finally, Section V summarizes the paper and draws conclusions.

II. POWER SYSTEM DYNAMICS MODEL

DSE refers to estimating the dynamic state existing in the power system, such as rotor angle and speed of the generators. Generally, these dynamics are modeled using two types of equations: differential and algebraic equations. The general discrete-time form of power system dynamics model is given as follows [24].

$$\begin{cases} x_k = f(x_{k-1}, u_k) + q_k \\ z_k = h(x_{k-1}, u_k) + r_k, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where k denotes the time step, the state vector x includes the rotor angle δ and the speed ω of the generators, which are key indicators of system stability. The input vector u includes the mechanical power input P^m and the internal voltage magnitude E of the generators. Moreover, the output vector z includes the voltage magnitude V and the phase angle θ of the terminals. The process noise q and the measurement noise r represent the uncertainty in the model and the measurement, respectively. These noises can arise from various sources, such as measurement errors, modeling inaccuracies, and disturbances in the system. The functions $f(\cdot)$ and $h(\cdot)$ represent the dynamics of the system and the measurement model, respectively. $f(\cdot)$ represents the swing equation of the generators, which describes the dynamics of the generator rotor angle and speed. $h(\cdot)$ represents the power flow equation, which describes the relationship between the magnitude of the voltage and phase angle at the terminals.

A. Measurement Model

Power system analysis is primarily focused on the generator state. This is because power system instability is mostly caused

by mechanical limitations of the generator [25]. Therefore, the measurement model is derived using the concepts of Kron reduction. Ward admittance models the interconnection of voltages and currents at different nodes in the system, while Kron reduction reduces the dimensionality of the system by eliminating the non-generator nodes. The measurement model is derived from the following equation [26]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y_{GG} & Y_{GL} \\ Y_{LG} & Y_{LL} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E\angle\delta \\ V\angle\theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} I_G\angle\delta \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $E\angle\delta$ and $V\angle\theta$ represent the generator voltage and load voltage, respectively. $I_G\angle\delta$ represents the current of the generator. The admittance matrix models the interconnection of voltages and currents at different nodes in the system and contains sub-matrices, such as the admittance between generators (Y_{GG}), admittance between generators and loads (Y_{GL} and Y_{LG}), and admittance between loads (Y_{LL}).

From (2), the relationship between internal voltage and terminal voltage can be expressed as

$$V\angle\theta = (-Y_{LL}^{-1})Y_{LG}E\angle\delta = Y_M E\angle\delta. \quad (3)$$

However, since Y_M is not a square matrix, to calculate the internal voltage from PMU data, the inverse matrix of Y_M must be obtained using methods such as the Moore-Penrose method. The Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse matrix is a generalization of the matrix inverse that is useful for solving linear equations with singular or near-singular coefficient matrices. The pseudoinverse can be defined as

$$(Y_M)^+ = ((Y_M)^T Y_M)^{-1} (Y_M)^T, \quad (4)$$

where $(Y_M)^+$ represents the pseudoinverse of the matrix Y_M , and $(Y_M)^T$ represents the transpose of the matrix Y_M . Using the pseudoinverse $(Y_M)^+$, the relationship between internal voltage and terminal voltage can be re-expressed as

$$E\angle\delta = (Y_M)^+ V\angle\theta. \quad (5)$$

If the internal voltage is obtained from (5), the rotor angle can be calculated using the following equation:

$$\delta = \tan^{-1} \frac{\text{Im}(E\angle\delta)}{\text{Re}(E\angle\delta)}. \quad (6)$$

B. State Space Model

The swing equation describes the evolution of the rotor angle δ and their relative frequency $\Delta\omega$, which is defined as the difference between the generator speed ω and the rated speed ω_s . The fundamental model of the swing equation can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\delta_i}{dt} = \omega_i - \omega_s \\ \frac{d^2\delta_i}{dt^2} = \frac{1}{2H_i} (P_i^m - P_i^e - D_i\Delta\omega_i), \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where i indicates the generator index, H is the inertia constant of the generator, P^m indicates the mechanical power input to the generator, P^e indicates the electrical power output of the generator, and D is the damping coefficient that considers the

Fig. 1. Concept of DSE using LMS algorithm.

energy losses in the generator and its control systems. The electrical power output P^e can be calculated as follows:

$$P_i^e = E_i^2 G_{ii} + \sum_{j \neq i}^n E_i E_j \{ G_{ij} \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j) + B_{ij} \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j) \}, \quad (8)$$

where G and B represent the real and imaginary parts of reduced matrix Y_{eq} . Using Kron reduction, Y_{eq} can be derived as

$$Y_{eq} = Y_{GG} - Y_{GL} Y_{LL}^{-1} Y_{LG}. \quad (9)$$

III. PROPOSED DYNAMIC STATE ESTIMATION METHOD

In this section, we propose a DSE method using the LMS algorithm. Unlike the Kalman filter-based method, the proposed method does not have a separate correction term. The proposed method directly corrects the internal model parameter using the LMS algorithm. In the Kalman filter algorithm, the Kalman gains are updated from the linearization model and the Gaussian covariance; however, the proposed method is mathematically much more concise by updating the weights W_k and the bias b_k . Fig. 1 shows the concept of the proposed DSE method. When the $\hat{\delta}_k$ is estimated from (7) and pseudo-measurement δ_k is calculated from (5) and (6), this method updates the weight W_k and the bias b_k . It is then used to update the previous estimated state $\hat{\omega}_k$ to $\hat{\omega}_k^-$ for the next estimate.

$$\hat{\omega}_k^- = W_k \hat{x}_k + b_k \quad (10)$$

$$\hat{\omega}_{k+1} = \hat{\omega}_k^- + \dot{\delta}_{k+1} \Delta t \quad (11)$$

$$\hat{\delta}_{k+1} = \hat{\delta}_k + \dot{\delta}_{k+1} \Delta t \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\omega}_k^-$ indicates the updated parameter, \hat{x}_k indicates the previous estimated state, including the estimated angle $\hat{\delta}_k$ and the estimated speed $\hat{\omega}_k$. Moreover, $\dot{\delta}_{k+1}$, $\dot{\delta}_{k+1}$ are derivatives of the rotor angle and speed, respectively, calculated from (7).

To update the weights W_k and the bias b_k , the LMS algorithm has the following loss function:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2} (\delta_{k+1} - \hat{\delta}_{k+1})^2, \quad (13)$$

However, the rotor angle calculated from equations (7) and (12) is an integral value, so it is not limited by $\pm\pi$. Therefore, the deviation of the rotor angle may be computed with a value exceeding $\pm 2\pi$, causing an error in the LMS algorithm. For this reason, before applying the LMS algorithm, the loss function must be modified as follows:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sin^2(\delta_{k+1} - \hat{\delta}_{k+1})}{2}, \quad (14)$$

where δ_{k+1} indicates the rotor angle calculated from (5) and (6), $\hat{\delta}_{k+1}$ indicates the rotor angle estimated from (12).

The loss function in (14) can be used to update the weight W_k and the bias b_k as

$$W_{k+1} = W_k - \eta \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial W}, \quad (15)$$

$$b_{k+1} = b_k - \eta \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial b}, \quad (16)$$

where η indicates the learning rate. Therefore, the update equation of the weight W_k and the bias b_k can be derived simply as

$$W_{k+1} = W_k + \frac{\eta \sin(2(\delta_{k+1} - \hat{\delta}_{k+1})) \Delta t x_k}{2}, \quad (17)$$

$$b_{k+1} = b_k + \frac{\eta \sin(2(\delta_{k+1} - \hat{\delta}_{k+1})) \Delta t}{2}. \quad (18)$$

These update equations are much simpler than those involved in the update step of the Kalman filter. See the Appendix for the general equation of the EKF-based method. The EKF-based method involves finding the Jacobian of nonlinear functions $f(\cdot)$ and $h(\cdot)$ on x_k for the Kalman gain update. On the other hand, the proposed method finds the Jacobian of the less nonlinear function ε on W_k and b_k for $\hat{\omega}_k^-$ update. This reduces the error introduced by the Jacobian approximation. Additionally, in the EKF-based method, calculation of the covariance P_k and the state x_k is required to update the Kalman gain; conversely, the proposed method only needs to calculate the state x_k . In other words, the amount of computations can be reduced by reducing the amount of computations required to compute the covariance P_k . Therefore, it can be inferred that the proposed method will be faster and more accurate than the EKF-based method. It is verified by the simulation results discussed in the next section.

IV. CASE STUDIES

To demonstrate the superiority of the proposed method, its performance was tested on a WSCC 9-bus system and compared with the EKF method. The topology of the WSCC 9-bus test system is shown in Fig. 2. The system contains nine buses and three generators and has four voltage levels: 13.8 kV, 16.5 kV, 18 kV and 230 kV. It is assumed that all generators are synchronous generators, the inertias H are 12, 6, and 3 s, and all the damping coefficients D are 0.001. Since the initial rotational motion of the synchronous generator must be supplied externally, the generator operates as a source for the first 1.5 s of the simulation.

To consider various actual scenarios, simulations were performed for the following three cases.

Fig. 2. WSCC 9-bus test system [27].

- Case 1: Normal operating condition where no events occur. The output of all generators remains stable.
- Case 2: Disturbance condition caused by a fault on bus 7. A 3-phase fault occurs at 7 s and is maintained for 2 cycles. The fault resistance is 0.01Ω .
- Case 3: Power injection change due to added load on bus 4. 31.5 MW load adds at 7 s.

The proposed method and the EKF-based method were implemented using Python 3.7 and co-simulated using PSCAD 5.0 on a 2.9 GHz personal computer. The estimation results of all scenarios were compared and analyzed by considering the root mean square error (RMSE).

A. Case 1: Normal operating condition

Fig. 3 illustrates the rotor angle and speed estimation results for three generators in Case 1. The black solid lines in the figure correspond to the actual value obtained using PSCAD. The blue dash lines indicate the estimated value using the EKF-based method, and the red dash lines represent the estimated value using the proposed method. Under normal operating conditions, both the EKF-based method and the proposed method can estimate the actual value normally. However, performance differences exist in terms of the estimation speed. The EKF-based method takes more than 5 s to accurately estimate the actual value; however, the proposed method almost accurately estimates the actual value after 1.5 s when the generator is switched from source to machine. The outcome shows that the proposed method has a higher estimation speed. This difference becomes more pronounced as the inertia gets smaller. In the EKF-based method, generator 3 with a small inertia responds more sensitively to a state change than generator 1 with a large inertia. This is because the smaller the inertia of the generator, the higher the variability. Meanwhile, the proposed method shows a relatively stable estimation performance, regardless of the inertia. This indicates that the proposed method has faster and higher adaptability than EKF-based methods.

B. Case 2 : Disturbance condition

Fig. 4 presents the rotor angle and speed estimation results for three generators in Case 2. The trajectory for 7 s before

Fig. 3. Case 1: Normal operating condition where no events occur. (a), (b) present the rotor angles of generator 1, (c), (d) present the rotor angles of generator 2, (e), (f) present the rotor angles of the generator 3.

the 3-phase failure occurs is the same as the result of Case 1. However, both the EKF-based and proposed methods exhibit poor estimation performance immediately after the fault occurs because the DSE considers the previous state (pre-fault state) estimate. In particular, under these abnormal operating conditions, the proposed method is more sensitive than the EKF-based method. However, as discussed in case 1, the proposed method exhibits better estimation performance as soon as a new operating point can be estimated because it has faster and higher adaptability. EKF-based methods take longer to estimate a new operating point. In the simulation, the estimate at generator 2, which is close to the fault point, was most affected, and the estimate at generator 1, which has a large inertia, was least affected.

C. Case 3: Power injection change

Fig. 5 shows the rotor angle and speed estimation results for three generators in Case 3. As in Case 2, the error occurs as soon as a sudden load change occurs. The proposed method shows better estimation performance as soon as a new operating point can be estimated. Conversely, the EKF-based method takes longer to estimate a new operating point. In the EKF-based method, the estimate at generator 1, which is close to the load addition point, is also high affected. However, the estimate at generators 2 and 3, which has a relatively small inertia, are also significantly affected. However, the proposed

Fig. 4. Case 2 : Disturbance condition caused by a fault on bus 7. (a), (b) present the rotor angles of generator 1, (c), (d) present the rotor angles of generator 2, (e), (f) present the rotor angles of the generator 3.

Fig. 5. Case 3: Power injection change caused by the added load on bus 4. (a), (b) present the rotor angles of generator 1, (c), (d) present the rotor angles of generator 2, (e), (f) present the rotor angles of generator 3.

method exhibits relatively stable estimation performance, regardless of the inertia even in Case 3.

Fig. 6 presents a comparison of the RMSE performance of the estimators in Cases 1, 2, and 3. Here, the dash lines represent the RMSE of the EKF-based method and the solid lines represent the RMSE of the proposed method. In all three cases, the proposed method exhibits a lower RMSE than that of the EKF-based method. The result proves that the proposed method has a higher estimation performance than the EKF-based method. In particular, the proposed method maintains relatively stable performance under abnormal operating conditions, regardless of the inertia.

Table I summarizes the simulation results obtained in this study. In all simulated cases, the proposed method has a smaller RMSE than the EKF-based method. This can be attributed to the faster and higher adaptability of the proposed method. Moreover, the runtime is 2 to 3 times faster than that of the EKF-based method. This is because the update formula of the proposed method is much more concise, as described in Section III. Therefore, the proposed method presents the likelihood of being applied to more complex and larger systems.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a DSE method based on the LMS algorithm is proposed. Unlike the Kalman filter algorithm, which updates

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF ESTIMATION PERFORMANCE

		Kalman Filter (EKF)	LMS Algorithm (Proposed)
Case 1	RMSE(δ)	0.8531 rad	0.4469 rad
	RMSE(ω)	21.1407 rad/s	14.3536 rad/s
Case 2	RMSE(δ)	1.0716 rad	0.4494 rad
	RMSE(ω)	21.1608 rad/s	14.3562 rad/s
Case 3	RMSE(δ)	1.5360 rad	0.5938 rad
	RMSE(ω)	21.1448 rad/s	14.3536 rad/s
Runtime		0.6536 ms	0.2439 ms

the correction term, the proposed method directly updates a parameter inside the mathematical model. The LMS-based method utilizes a mathematical model while providing adaptability to the measurement data. Unlike existing AI-based methods, prior data is not required because the proposed method estimates using real-time measurement data only. Moreover, the method is mathematically simple; therefore, it does not require extensive calculations. In the simulation, the proposed method was compared with the EKF-based method for three cases: normal, fault, and power injection. Simulation results show that the proposed method was 2 to 3 times faster and more accurate than the EKF-based method. Therefore,

Fig. 6. Root mean square error(RMSE) for each cases. (a), (b) present the rotor angle and speed estimation performance of Case 1, (c), (d) present the rotor angle and speed estimation performance in Case 2, (e), (f) present the rotor angle and speed estimation performance in Case 3

the proposed method can be applied to power systems that are larger and contain many components. However, since the proposed method reacts more sensitively to fault, it is necessary to discuss an appropriate loss function to improve robustness for future work.

APPENDIX A EXTENDED KALMAN FILTER

EKF is a commonly used algorithm for dynamic state estimation in nonlinear systems. It can minimize the covariance of estimation errors. EKF has a two-step process of prediction and correction.

In the prediction step, the state x_k is predicted based on the previous state x_{k-1} using the differential equation (7). In the correction step, the predicted state \hat{x}_k^- is corrected with the error between the measurement z_k and $h(\hat{x}_k^-)$. Therefore, the equations for EKF is given as

Prediction Step:

$$\hat{x}_k^- = f(\hat{x}_{k-1}^+, u_k), \quad (A1)$$

$$P_k^- = A_k P_{k-1} A_k^T + Q. \quad (A2)$$

Correction Step:

$$K_k = \frac{P_k^- H_k^T}{H_k P_k^- H_k^T + R_k}, \quad (A3)$$

$$\hat{x}_k^+ = \hat{x}_k^- + K_k (z_k - h(\hat{x}_k^-)), \quad (A4)$$

$$P_k = P_k^- - K_k H_k P_k^-, \quad (A5)$$

where K indicates the Kalman gain, P indicates the estimation error covariance, Q indicates the process noise covariance, R indicates the measurement noise covariance.

From (7) and (8), The Jacobian A can be derived as follows:

$$x_k = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_k \\ \omega_k \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{k-1} + \omega_{k-1} \Delta t \\ \omega_{k-1} + \frac{1}{2H_i} (P_{k-1}^m - P_{k-1}^e - D \Delta \omega_{k-1}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (A6)$$

$$A = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \delta_k}{\partial \delta_{k-1}} & \frac{\partial \delta_k}{\partial \omega_{k-1}} \\ \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \delta_{k-1}} & \frac{\partial \omega_k}{\partial \omega_{k-1}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (A7)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t \\ \frac{\sum_{j \neq i}^n E_i E_j \{G_{ij} \sin(\delta_i - \delta_j) - B_{ij} \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j)\}}{2H_i} & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Similarly, The Jacobian H can be derived as follow:

$$z_k = \begin{bmatrix} Re(V_k \angle \theta_k) \\ Im(V_k \angle \theta_k) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} G_M E_k \cos(\delta_k) - B_M E_k \sin(\delta_k) \\ G_M E_k \sin(\delta_k) + B_M E_k \cos(\delta_k) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (A8)$$

$$H = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial Re(V_k \angle \theta_k)}{\partial \delta_k} & \frac{\partial Re(V_k \angle \theta_k)}{\partial \omega_k} \\ \frac{\partial Im(V_k \angle \theta_k)}{\partial \delta_k} & \frac{\partial Im(V_k \angle \theta_k)}{\partial \omega_k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (A9)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} -G_M E_k \sin(\delta_k) - B_M E_k \cos(\delta_k) & 0 \\ G_M E_k \cos(\delta_k) - B_M E_k \sin(\delta_k) & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

where G_M and B_M are the real and imaginary parts of Y_M matrix. $Re(V_k \angle \theta_k)$ and $Im(V_k \angle \theta_k)$ are the real and imaginary parts of $V_k \angle \theta_k$.

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